

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

Results of dissemination and communication activities – Initial version

March 2021

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Executive summary

ARTwin is a Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action, aiming to develop and introduce an easily deployable platform that enables the design and maintenance of highly accurate digital representations of real environments, be they factories or construction sites (Digital Twin or BIM), that are updated in real time and allow for the deployment of high-quality interactive services, well-tailored to the requirements of Industry and Construction 4.0.

In this context, creating awareness, communicating and disseminating the value propositions, activities and results of ARTwin is of utmost importance. Task 6.1 is devoted to developing a tailored strategy and plan for dissemination, and awareness raising and communication with a view to effectively conveying the key messages of ARTwin to its target audiences as well as increasing the visibility of the project along with its activities and results, thus paving the road for their post-project rollout and uptake.

This report is titled “Results of dissemination and communication activities – Initial Version” and has been elaborated as a deliverable (D6.4) in the framework of the ARTwin project. It is an initial report outlining the dissemination and communication activities of the project as well as their results. An updated and final version will be delivered by the end of the project.

1. Introduction

This report, titled “**Results of dissemination and communication activities – Initial Version**” has been elaborated as a deliverable (D6.4) in the framework of the ARTwin project. It is an initial report outlining the dissemination and communication activities during the first 18 months of the project as well as their results. It is related to Task 6.1, devoted to developing and implementing a tailored strategy and plan for dissemination, awareness raising and communication with a view to effectively conveying the key messages of ARTwin to its target audiences as well as increasing the visibility of the project along with its activities and results, thus paving the road for their post-project rollout and uptake.

Taking into account the previously described, this report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** addresses the development of ARTwin’s visual identify along with a basic promotional package (logo, colour palette, poster, leaflet, general presentation, etc.).
- **Chapter 3** provides an overview of the implemented dissemination, communication and awareness raising activities of the project (website, social media, external events, newsletters, publications, etc.) along with their results.
- **Chapter 4** reflects the progress of the dissemination activities according to the key performance indicators (KPIs) set for the communication and dissemination activities.
- **Chapter 5** presents the conclusions of the report.

With the above in mind, this is the **first version of the report on the results of dissemination and communication activities** produced by the end and covering the activities implemented in the first period of the project as well as their results. A second version of the report will be drafted at the end of the project (i.e. as D6.7 in M36) in order to reflect and take into account the dissemination and communication activities during the second period of the project.

2. Visual identity and promotional package

Since the beginning of the project, different work has been done on the visual identity of ARTwin, which is key for an effective dissemination of the project so the different materials developed in the framework of the project can be easily identified and related to the project itself. In addition, different elements have been developed for the promotion and dissemination of ARTwin, including the logo, leaflet and poster, general presentation and templates, which are described in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Logo

ARTwin's logo was developed in the beginning of the project (M1) and has been approved by all partners.

Figure 1. ARTwin's logo

2.2 Leaflet

A project leaflet has been prepared using the logo's colour palette. The leaflet describes the aim and goals of ARTwin, the consortium, the services that are being developed in the project and the benefits to the respective target users, the project identity data, the contact details and links to the website and social media pages. The following figures show both sides of the leaflet, which has been provided to all partners.

Figure 2. ARTwin leaflet side A

TAKE YOUR FACTORY OR CONSTRUCTION TO THE NEXT LEVEL

ARTwin introduces an easily deployable ARCloud platform that enables the design and maintenance of highly accurate digital representations (digital twins) of large-scale operational environments, that are updated in real time and allow for the deployment of high quality interactive services, well-tailored to the requirements of Industry and Construction 4.0.

SERVICES

- Development and updating of a unified global map of the factory or construction site**
A unified map representing the geometry of large-scale real environments will be specified and updated in real-time by various input data and serve as the bedrock for the provision of cutting-edge services.
- Localization service to track AR devices**
A robust and accurate localization system will be developed, allowing for large-scale real time localization based on the unified map and capable to account for the large variability of the environment.
- Development and real-time updating of a 3D digital twin of a factory or BIM of a construction site**
A Digital Twin/ BIM real-time updating system will be built, to ease factory planning adaptation and allow the effective monitoring of construction progress and defect detection.
- AR Remote Rendering service for displaying complex 3D models on low-resource AR devices**
An AR remote rendering service will be delivered, in order to overcome the limitations of the computational power of existing and future devices, offering the ability to render complex 3D models with ultra-low latency.

USE CASES / PILOTS

By means of a 5G network, the ARTwin solution will be deployed in major real-life pilots in Siemens factories and large construction sites, so as to:

- Provide contextually and spatially correct augmentations to factory workers about the machines they are operating (or monitoring) through AR devices.
- Enable flexibility and automation in the re-planning of dynamic production lines, through the use of the real-time digital twin of the factory along with interactive AR/VR editing capabilities.
- Offer scale 1:1 multi-user AR (tobis) that will assist construction managers in detecting defects and help the workers retrieve relevant information for each task, minimizing the risks and producing better constructions.

BENEFITS

- Optimize your operations and increase your productivity & flexibility**
The ARTwin solution enables proactive problem detection and assisted problem solving, inducing maximum efficiency in the performance of tasks. It helps increase the productivity and flexibility by contributing to effective production or construction design, planning and re-adaptation, leading to improved product quality and reduced costs.
- Capitalize on knowledge flows**
The disruptive improvements offered by the ARTwin solution can enhance communication and information flows, as well as facilitate the integration, sharing and use of new knowledge, reducing training needs and stimulating innovation on individual, intra- and inter-organizational level.
- Save time and minimize risks**
With the ARTwin solution, factory workers can document changes and suggest improvements in seconds rather than hours, operators can reach critical decisions in seconds rather than minutes, factory planners can change layouts in minutes rather than days and construction site workers can execute their tasks with minimum defects.

The ARTwin cutting-edge solution for increased productivity and product quality in Industry and Construction 4.0.

Figure 3. ARTwin leaflet side B

2.3 Poster

The poster of ARTwin has been created following the same layout designed for the project. This poster can be used in stands or booths, when a partner participates in third-party events.

ARTWIN
INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

AUGMENTING YOUR OPERATION PROCESSES TO MAXIMIZE PRODUCTIVITY AND PRODUCT QUALITY

QPLAN | b.com | SIEMENS | A&E | NOKIA | HeLight | A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 851994.

Figure 4. ARTwin poster

2.4 Templates

Templates have been created for the consortium partners to be able to produce their project deliverables and their presentations. In particular, a template for the project's deliverables (both internal and public) as well as a template for the partners' presentations have been created and made available to project partners.

Figure 5. ARTwin deliverables' templates

2.5 Presentation

A standard presentation of ARTwin was produced for use at workshops, conferences, info days and other events organised or attended by ARTwin partners. The presentation can be found in Annex I.

Figure 6. ARTwin standard presentation

3. Dissemination activities and their results

3.1 Usage of the ARTwin website

The ARTwin website serves as the primary online platform to provide information about ARTwin, the project objectives, concept and results and provides access to news about the project. The ARTwin website also cross links with all the social media channels of the project.

Activities related to the website during the first 18 months consisted in:

- Defining the content and structure of the website
- Booking the domain names and setting up the IT infrastructure
- Designing, developing and publishing the website
- Refining the existing content and adding new content (news, results, etc.)

Since the launch of the website on January 2020 until March 2021, there were 1.656 sessions by 1.062 users for a total of 3.950 page views. An average session duration on the website is 2:26 minutes (counted as the period of time a user is actively engaged with the website).

Figure 7. ARTwin web portal traffic. Source: Google Analytics.

Concerning the audience, 85,5% are returning visitors, while 14,5% are new visitors. Thus, we can make a positive conclusion that ARTwin attracts new visitors who would like to learn more about the project and its development.

Figure 8. ARTwin web portal: new visitors vs returning visitors. Source: Google Analytics

The most popular countries among our audience are France (167 users), Germany (151 users), Greece (128 users), United States (90 users), China (42 users), India (40), Austria (34), Brazil (34), Canada (33) and Czechia (30).

Figure 9. ARTwin web portal: geographical scope of audience. Source: Google Analytics

Country ?	Acquisition			Behaviour			Conversions		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?	Goal Conversion Rate ?	Goal Completions ?	Goal Value ?
	1,062 <small>% of Total: 100.00% (1,062)</small>	1,067 <small>% of Total: 100.19% (1,065)</small>	1,656 <small>% of Total: 100.00% (1,656)</small>	57.07% <small>Avg for View: 57.07% (0.00%)</small>	2.39 <small>Avg for View: 2.39 (0.00%)</small>	00:02:26 <small>Avg for View: 00:02:26 (0.00%)</small>	0.00% <small>Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)</small>	0 <small>% of Total: 0.00% (0)</small>	US\$0.00 <small>% of Total: 0.00% (US\$0.00)</small>
1. France	167 (15.53%)	165 (15.46%)	264 (15.94%)	54.17%	2.44	00:01:45	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. Germany	151 (14.05%)	150 (14.06%)	245 (14.79%)	48.16%	2.72	00:03:12	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. Greece	128 (11.91%)	130 (12.18%)	329 (19.87%)	46.50%	2.56	00:03:50	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. United States	90 (8.37%)	91 (8.53%)	98 (5.92%)	81.63%	1.62	00:01:07	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
5. China	42 (3.91%)	42 (3.94%)	42 (2.54%)	92.86%	1.21	00:00:03	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
6. India	40 (3.72%)	40 (3.75%)	52 (3.14%)	69.23%	1.73	00:01:16	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
7. Austria	34 (3.16%)	31 (2.91%)	42 (2.54%)	50.00%	2.88	00:01:02	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
8. Brazil	34 (3.16%)	34 (3.19%)	37 (2.23%)	94.59%	1.05	00:00:04	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
9. Canada	33 (3.07%)	33 (3.09%)	33 (1.99%)	96.97%	1.03	00:00:01	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
10. Czechia	30 (2.79%)	30 (2.81%)	58 (3.50%)	62.07%	2.21	00:02:28	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)

Show rows: 10 Go to: 1 1-10 of 58

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Figure 10. ARTwin web portal: metrics of top 10 countries. Source: Google Analytics.

The information on the most visited pages demonstrates that apart from regular landing pages, such as “Team”, “Advisory Board” and “Concept and objectives”, visitors are mostly interested in the ARTwin platform and the use cases.

Page ?	Page Views ?	Unique Page Views ?	Avg. Time on Page ?	Entrances ?	Bounce Rate ?	% Exit ?	Page Value ?
	3,950 % of Total: 100.00% (3,950)	3,323 % of Total: 100.00% (3,323)	00:01:45 Avg for View: 00:01:45 (0.00%)	1,653 % of Total: 100.00% (1,653)	57.07% Avg for View: 57.07% (0.00%)	41.85% Avg for View: 41.85% (0.00%)	US\$0.00 % of Total: 0.00% (US\$0.00)
1. /	1,467 (37.14%)	1,166 (35.09%)	00:02:05	1,092 (66.06%)	54.48%	52.08%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. /index.php/the-team/	317 (8.03%)	266 (8.00%)	00:01:30	49 (2.96%)	51.02%	33.75%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. /index.php/advisory-board/	294 (7.44%)	261 (7.85%)	00:02:46	126 (7.62%)	66.67%	53.74%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. /index.php/concept-objectives/	237 (6.00%)	203 (6.11%)	00:02:16	27 (1.63%)	65.38%	39.66%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
5. /index.php/the-platform/	172 (4.35%)	151 (4.54%)	00:01:09	24 (1.45%)	50.00%	25.58%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
6. /index.php/newsletter/	112 (2.84%)	84 (2.53%)	00:02:35	51 (3.09%)	49.02%	46.43%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
7. /index.php/ar-enabled-factory-worker/	109 (2.76%)	97 (2.92%)	00:00:33	10 (0.60%)	80.00%	22.94%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
8. /index.php/relevant-initiatives/	100 (2.53%)	87 (2.62%)	00:02:01	16 (0.97%)	64.71%	39.00%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
9. /index.php/latest-news/	94 (2.38%)	84 (2.53%)	00:01:21	15 (0.91%)	37.50%	22.34%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
10. /index.php/unified-global-map/	94 (2.38%)	85 (2.56%)	00:01:30	25 (1.51%)	52.00%	23.40%	US\$0.00 (0.00%)

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Figure 11. ARTwin web portal: most visited pages. Source: Google Analytics.

The following image shows where the traffic on the ARTwin web portal comes from. We can conclude that direct landing, organic search, social media and referral from other links are the 4 top routes leading to the website so far.

Default Channel Grouping	Acquisition			Behaviour			Conversions		
	Users ?	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?	Goal Conversion Rate ?	Goal Completions ?	Goal Value ?
	1,062 % of Total: 100.00% (1,062)	1,067 % of Total: 100.19% (1,065)	1,656 % of Total: 100.00% (1,656)	57.07% Avg for View: 57.07% (0.00%)	2.39 Avg for View: 2.39 (0.00%)	00:02:26 Avg for View: 00:02:26 (0.00%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)	0 % of Total: 0.00% (0)	US\$0.00 % of Total: 0.00% (US\$0.00)
1. Direct	501 (45.30%)	501 (46.95%)	756 (45.65%)	58.86%	2.33	00:02:19	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. Organic Search	416 (37.61%)	395 (37.02%)	660 (39.86%)	52.12%	2.59	00:02:45	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. Social	123 (11.12%)	115 (10.78%)	159 (9.60%)	66.04%	1.91	00:02:12	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. Referral	66 (5.97%)	56 (5.25%)	81 (4.89%)	62.96%	2.11	00:01:24	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	US\$0.00 (0.00%)

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Figure 12. ARTwin web portal: source of website traffic. Source: Google Analytics.

From the above graphics and figures, we can conclude that efforts need to be made in the next period to:

- Increase the traffic to the website.
- Increase the traffic through organic search and through social and referral.

To achieve this, we will need to work on several fronts:

- Content: There is a need to improve the content available on the website. This will certainly be the case when the ARTwin pilots are set in motion and we have actual results from the ARTwin platform in the field (parallel development of ARTwin promotional video).
- Generating more back links to the website to generate more traffic through referrals.

3.2 Newsletter

Online newsletter distribution provides the opportunity to increase public and stakeholders’ awareness of the project, assists increasing the outreach to the target audience and maintaining contact with it, and encourages readers to find out more about the project, including links to more detailed information on project’s website.

Within ARTwin dissemination activities, an online newsletter was regularly distributed among various project stakeholders and the newsletter subscribers, on a semester basis. Two issues of the ARTwin newsletter have been released, until the end of M19 (April 2021) whereas the third issue is currently under preparation.

For the distribution of the newsletter, the professional web marketing solution MailChimp was used. After its release, the newsletter was published on the project’s official web portal and is further disseminated through the project’s social media accounts.

The basic distribution list contains 71 stakeholders who have subscribed to the newsletter through the respective section on the ARTwin web portal.

Top locations

Figure 13. Newsletter geo statistics.
Source: Mailchimp

3.3 Social media accounts

3.3.1 Usage of Twitter channel

The project Twitter channel was established in November 2019. The dissemination efforts on the Twitter channel include compiling short messages which can be posted on this channel. To this end, the Dissemination Manager seeks for general messages which could be relevant for our stakeholders and increase our followers base. Several sources are used to compile messages:

- by searching on relevant acknowledged sources of information such as the European Factories of the Future Research Association, EuroXR, etc.
- Retweet content twitted by our followers or by potential influencers identified by the Dissemination Manager. When twitting these messages, chances are increased to engage these influencers and widen our outreach.

In the first period of ARTwin, the Twitter channel was mainly used to virally spread out news and messages, especially information about the project’s concept, partner activities, etc., in order to start building an online presence and widen our network comprised from relevant stakeholders.

At the time of writing this deliverable (March 2021), the ARTwin’s twitter account counts 312 followers.

Figure 14. Followers of ARTwin twitter page during the last 18 months. Source: Twitter

Figure 15. Profile visits of ARTwin twitter page during the last 18 months. Source: Twitter

Figure 16. ARTwin tweet impressions during the last 18 months. Source: Twitter.

The above graphics and figures show that the engagement strategy followed for the twitter channel started to bring satisfactory results. The channel is set to grow but there is a need to step up the related efforts as there is a great potential to build a big followers base on twitter.

3.3.2 Usage of LinkedIn channel

On LinkedIn, the ARTwin project is active with a company account. The account was launched in November 2019 and currently it has 332 followers.

Figure 17. ARTwin LinkedIn follower statistics from March 2020 to March 2021. Source: LinkedIn.

Figure 18. Follower demographics of the LinkedIn page. Source: Twitter

Visitor metrics Time range: Feb 29, 2020 - Feb 27, 2021 Page: All Pages Metric: Page views

Aggregate desktop and mobile traffic Off

Visitor demographics Time range: Feb 29, 2020 - Feb 27, 2021 Data for: Job function

Top job functions

Figure 19. Visitors of the LinkedIn page of ARTwin from Feb 2020 to Feb 2021. Source: LinkedIn

Figure 20. ARTwin LinkedIn posts statistics from Feb 2020 to Feb 2021. Source: LinkedIn.

3.3.3 Usage of Facebook channel

The Facebook account was established on November 2019 and is seen as an important channel to publish relevant news, events and information relative to the ARTwin project. As of March 2021, the Facebook page of ARTwin counts 112 page likes and 119 followers. Since the account was created, a lot of posts were published by the Dissemination Manager at least on monthly basis.

3.4 Publications

Throughout the project lifetime scientific publications assisted in informing the academic and research community as well as the industry and general public about the project’s objectives, scientific activities, findings and results. Scientific knowledge generated during the project is already being shared in popular and high ranked scientific conferences and journals, as shown in the table below.

Table 1. ARTwin list of publications

Authors	Title	Conference/ Journal	Partner	Date	Available at:
Timothy Duff, Kathlén Kohn, Anton Leykin, Tomas Pajdla	Point-line Minimal Problems under Partial Visibility in Three Views	Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR) 2020	CTU	14 – 19 June 2020	Link
M Polic, S Steidl, C Albl, Z Kukulova, T Pajdla	Uncertainty Based Camera Model Selection	Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR) 2020	CTU	14 – 19 June 2020	Link

R Fabbri, T Duff, H Fan, M H Regan, D da Costa de Pinho, E Tsigaridas, C W Wampler, J D Hauenstein, P J Giblin, B Kimia, A Leykin, T Pajdla	TRPLP – Trifocal Relative Pose From Lines at Points	Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR) 2020	CTU	14 – 19 June 2020	Link
C Albl, Z Kukelova, V Larsson, M Polic, T Pajdla, K Schindler	From two rolling shutters to one global shutter	Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR) 2020	CTU	14 – 19 June 2020	Link
Daniel Barath, Michal Polic, Wolfgang Förstner, Torsten Sattler, Tomas Pajdla, and Zuzana Kukelova	Making Affine Correspondences Work in Camera Geometry Computation	European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV 2020)	CTU	23 - 28 August 2020	Link
Federica Arrigoni, Luca Magri, and Tomas Pajdla	On the Usage of the Trifocal Tensor in Motion Segmentation	European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV 2020)	CTU	23 - 28 August 2020	Link
Timothy Duff, Kathlen Kohn, Anton Leykin, Tomas Pajdla	PL1P – Point-line Minimal Problems under Partial Visibility in Three Views	European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV 2020)	CTU	23 - 28 August 2020	Link
Zuzana Kukelova, Cenek Albl, Akihiro Sugimoto, Konrad Schindler, and Tomas Pajdla	Minimal Rolling Shutter Absolute Pose with Unknown Focal Length and Radial Distortion	European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV 2020)	CTU	23 - 28 August 2020	Link

The publications are provided in open access and they are also uploaded on Zenodo (offered to the Zenodo and OpenAIRE community) as well as on the project's web portal (<https://artwin-project.eu/index.php/publications-coming-soon/>). The public deliverables are published on the ARTwin web portal (<https://artwin-project.eu/index.php/reports/>) as well as on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=856994>) with open access once they are accepted by the EU.

3.5 External events

During the first period of ARTwin, partners have attended the following third-party events:

1. **Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference** (<http://cvpr2020.thecvf.com/>) CVPR 2020. This event, attended by CTU during 14-19 June, is one of the prime annual computer vision events.
2. QPL, BCM and HOL participated in the **Coordinator workshop on interactive technologies** that DG CONECT G2 held on 26 June 2020, presenting ARTwin and discussing emerging opportunities arising from the COVID-19 crisis for the XR techs as well as current or future XR solutions particularly well adapted to meet the new challenges of a post-COVID-19 world.
3. **European Conference on Computer Vision** (<https://eccv2020.eu/about-eccv/>) ECCV 2020. ECCV, one of the top European conferences in the image analysis area, was held online and was attended by CTU during 23 – 28 August 2020.
4. QPL attended the **Digital Twin Awareness Day**, which was organised by Bentley institute and COMIT and held online on Tuesday, the 22nd of September, 2020.
5. The ARTwin project was presented on October 21st 2020 in a **dedicated webinar hosted by the Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance (AREA)**. During this webinar BCM, ARTwin's technical coordinator, presented the project and described its current status.
6. BCM represented the ARTwin project in the **Interactive technologies workshop - Standards and Interoperability**, which was organised by DG CONECT on 21st of October 2020.
7. NBL and CTU represented the ARTwin project in the **Interactive technologies workshop - Awareness, Adoption and Acceptance**, which was organised by DG CONECT on 23rd of October 2020.
8. BCM and SIE take part in the **ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) on Augmented Reality Framework (ARF) group meetings** (two weekly meetings on reference point requirements and one monthly meeting on ARF open-source implementation)

3.6 Synergies

Synergies with other EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives in the relevant research domains are constantly pursued to facilitate knowledge exchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential collaborations. Possible synergies include (without being limited to) the following actions:

- inclusion of the project web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects,
- participation in events of similar projects,
- dissemination of ARTwin promotional material in events of similar projects,
- invitations to participate in ARTwin events
- exchange of news and dissemination through other projects' channels.

In this direction, during the first half of the project, ARTwin has collaborated with 3 key relevant H2020 projects (XR4ALL GA: 825545, iv4XR GA: 856716, IoTwins GA: 857191) in order to boost its visibility and outreach, including promotion through newsletter and website, exchange of follows/likes on social media, etc. Additionally, all seven projects from the same call as ARTWIN are promoted through the project website.

Further synergies established with initiatives, actions and networks across ARTwin’s social media channels have been a key element of the project’s dissemination and communication activities, enhancing the outreach of ARTwin to various additional stakeholders.

3.7 EU dissemination channels

During this period, the following dissemination channels have been used, in order to share with these organizations information related to the project and establish a first contact.

- CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service). CORDIS web where ARTwin consortium and objectives are published along with other project information as can be seen in next Figure.

Figure 21. ARTwin information on CORDIS

- ETSI ISG ARF. ETSI is a European Standards Organization (ESO), which is dealing with telecommunications, broadcasting and other electronic communications networks and services. ARTwin is contributing to ETSI standardisation activity and is promoted accordingly.
- Links on social media with different EU organisations, such as EIT Digital, Enterprise Europe Network, etc.

4. Performance indicators and monitoring

To measure the success of ARTwin’s awareness raising and communication strategy, the following KPIs have been employed and all dissemination activities along with their results are monitored and compared to these KPIs.

Table 2. Dissemination KPIs and progress against targets

Indicator (KPI)	Target Value (Impact)	Current status
Number of Scientific papers published	12 (in scientific conferences and journals)	8
Number of external events / conferences attended	30 events / conferences (research and industrial)	8

Synergies with major initiatives and networks	10 joint actions	3
Number of visits to the ARTwin web portal	12,000 unique visitors by the end of the project	1065 new users
Number of followers in the social media accounts	2,000 followers (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)	763 followers
Number of promotional materials distributed	2,000 copies distributed in project/ external events	0
Number of newsletters	6 newsletters (one per semester)	2
Number of workshops/ participants in each one	2 workshops/ 30 participants per workshop	-
Number of participants in the Final Conference	100 participants	-
Interactive technology and solution providers engaged	>100	-

It should be noted that since March 2020 (M6) the crisis due to COVID-19 affected the mobility of citizens of the European Union, as well as the holding of events, conferences, congresses, etc. where a significant number of people could be concentrated. This has undoubtedly affected the participation of the project consortium partners in different external events and the respective distribution of leaflets (only online events have been attended so no hard copies of promotional material has been distributed yet).

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to intensify the communication and dissemination actions in the forthcoming months, putting emphasis on the production of scientific publications emerging from the ARTwin research activities, the attendance of external conferences and events as well as the improvement of website visitors and social media followers.

5. Conclusions

This document presents the activities carried out so far (M18) in the field of dissemination and communication of the ARTwin project.

In the updated version of this deliverable, namely in “D6.7 Results of dissemination and communication activities – Final version”, which will be prepared at the end of the project, the cumulative impact of the ARTwin project will be presented.

Meanwhile, the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP) of the project will be updated in order to take into account the results of the dissemination efforts and will be submitted on M18.

Annex I – ARTwin standard presentation

Where it all begins

Current state of play

Digital twin is the key for improving lifecycle processes that are becoming increasingly digital in the factory!

BIM is becoming mainstream as it improves productivity, reduces changes and eases maintenance of the building!

Key current challenges

However...

-Updating digital representations is often costly and requires manual operation, therefore it is not carried out regularly. As a result, **models of the building or production environment quickly become outdated and obsolete.**

-Digital twins/ BIMs are mostly used by design offices. It is a real challenge to **present to on site workers the information extracted from the digital twin/ BIM at the right moment and overall at the right place.**

ARtwin comes into play

ARtwin will address these technical key challenges by:

- **Maintaining in real-time the digital twin/BIM using vision sensors** available in a factory or on the construction site
- Providing an **immersive visualization** of this digital twin/BIM both:
 - to **design offices**
 - to **operators in the field**

Who we are

The consortium

Our aspirations

Vision

ARTwin is set on providing the European Industry and Construction 4.0 ecosystem with a sovereign ARCloud platform that meets their ever-growing needs for increased productivity, improved product quality as well as reduced time and cost.

The solution

ARtwin ARCloud platform

An **autonomous and transportable all-in-one 5G solution**, which will account for the available technological capabilities and infrastructure of the user, **enabling optimal and cost-effective service delivery and seamless high-resolution AR experiences.**

The platform will **maintain in real-time the Digital Twin of the factory or BIM of the building**, using the vision sensors available in the factory or the construction site.

The services

The services

The use cases

AR enabled factory worker

This demonstrator will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will showcase the AR enabled factory worker.

In this use case, the factory workers will see all sorts of relevant information about the machine they are interacting with (operating, maintaining, monitoring, etc.) at a glance!

The information will help the workers to immediately understand the status of the machine, and they will be actionable!

Dynamic line planning

This use case demonstrator will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will leverage the ARTwin technologies to showcase dynamic production line planning.

In this use case, the production planning will be done using a VR enhanced planning tool that visualizes the current layout of the Digital Twin and provides interactive capabilities for the planners.

Alongside, this use case will demonstrate a real-time AR interface to factory planning tools, allowing also for field-level planners to use their AR device to make changes to the layout on site!

AR/VR assisted construction

This use case demonstrator will be deployed in the Eiffage Bretagne construction in Dinard, France and it will showcase the ARTwin technologies by providing AR/VR tools that will help the workers to construct more efficiently.

In this use case, workers will have a consistent AR view of the reference BIM model at a specific time of the construction and directly on site, through mobile devices or see-through headsets.

This feature will allow the site supervisor and the workers to work closely together even if the supervisor is at his/her office, using a VR device!

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ARTWIN

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